

Commentary

IL-18 and CD274 holds a promise to reduce asthma severity

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Purpose of Study.

Mishra et al recently establish in Allergy 2021 that anti-IL-18 and anti-CD274 neutralization improves asthma pathogenesis.

Study Population.

Eight- to 10-week-old BALB/c mice, interleukin, IL5 gene-deficient and GATA-1 gene-targeted mice, and IL-18-deficient inbred mice were maintained with age- and sex-matched controls.

Methods.

Using previously published protocols, mice were pretreated with anti-IL-18 and anti-CD274 followed by repeated inoculations of *Aspergillus fumigatus* antigens by intranasal routes. Eosinophils levels in the lung and airway hyperactivity were analyzed. The tissue distribution of eosinophils after intranasal allergen was examined in the blood, bronchoalveolar lavage fluid. Pathologic changes were defined using histologic examination of the

Lung and examining airway hyperactivity.

Reviewer's Comments.

Asthma is a complex, multi-faceted, allergic chronic heterogeneous disease of the lungs which characterized by the action of airway leading to reversible airflow obstruction in association with airway hyperresponsiveness (AHR) and airway inflammation. Asthma is affecting more than 300 million persons all over the world, including 25 million Americans. Despite significant advances in the management of asthma and development of several guidelines over the past decades, approximately 250,000 people die prematurely each year from asthma as per world health organization (WHO) estimates. Thus, more in-depth studies are warranted to identify underlying causes of asthma pathogenesis and identify novel therapeutic targets to reduce the severity of asthma.

Earlier reports indicate that IL-5 is a well-known growth and survival factor for eosinophils development and differentiation. Currently, anti-IL-5 therapy (i.e. mepolizumab, benralizumab,

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reslizumab) is commonly used to treat eosinophilic asthma. Although, the anti-IL-5 therapy has shown some promising effect by reducing the eosinophil mediated inflammation in asthmatic patients, but anti-IL-5 therapy is still not proven promising as expected. In recent studies by Mishra, *et al* indicated that there is possibility is that long-term use of anti-IL-5 therapy may have adverse effect on innate immune responses specially on the in gastrointestinal tract. Induced levels of IL-18 have been reported in allergic diseases including asthma. Previously, same group of investigators reported the role of IL-18 in transforming IL-5 generated naïve eosinophils into pathogenic CD274 expressing eosinophils in allergic diseases. In recent report Mishra *et al* have described the potential significance of IL-18 in regulating CD274 expressing eosinophils in promoting airway obstruction during asthma using *Aspergillus fumigatus* induced experimental models (wild type, IL5^{-/-}, IL-18^{-/-}, and eosinophil deficient GATA1-deficient mice). CD2IL-5 transgenic mice treated with recombinant (r) IL-18 have increased severity of asthma pathogenesis due to accumulation of eosinophils in peri-vascular and peri-bronchial regions of lung. Moreover, they showed rIL-18 treatment causes the development

of eosinophils mediated asthma pathogenesis even in eosinophil deficient GATA mice. They also showed that deletion of IL-5 and IL-18 by generating double IL-5^{-/-} IL-18^{-/-} double gene-deficient mice are further protected from the induction of CD274⁺ eosinophils mediated asthma. Most Importantly, reports indicated that neutralization of anti-IL-18 and and-CD274 protects asthma pathogenesis. Taken together, this preclinical findings from Mishra and colleagues suggest that IL-18 is critical for CD274 expressing eosinophils in asthma pathogenesis, and neutralization of anti-IL-18 and and-CD274 is a potential immunotherapeutic strategy for asthma.

Conclusion. Mishra *et al* recent finding in the Journal “Allergy December 2021” implicating the critical role of IL-18 and CD274 expressing eosinophils in asthma pathogenesis that has immense clinical potential to improve severity of asthma and thus lead a way to IL-18 targeted therapies for human asthma pathogenesis. Thus, prospective clinicals trial are required for anti-IL-18 anti-CD274 immunotherapy with proper control (placebo) to treat quality of life for asthmatic patients.

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